

Boerlagiomyces websteri (Ascomycota, Tubeufiaceae) from Hungary, first record outside the USA

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Received 2 February 2009 / Accepted 25 February 2009

Abstract. After a short review of the genus *Boerlagiomyces*, a short description of *B. websteri* is given and illustrated from material found in Hungary on old cherry stones.

Key words: *Ascomycetes*, *Boerlagiomyces websteri*, cherry stones, Hungary

Introduction

Boerlagiomyces Butzin, with seven known species, belongs to the Phylum *Ascomycota*, Subphylum *Pezizomycotina*, Class *Ascomycetes*, Order *Pleosporales*, Family *Tubeufiaceae*. It produces superficial, usually ostiolate and setose ascomata and transversally septate ascospores with vertical septa in most cells. Species of *Boerlagiomyces* are saprobes on decorticated wood of dicotyledonous plants decaying on soil or submerged in freshwater (comp. also Crane *et al.* 1998). *Boerlagiomyces* species have been reported mainly from tropical countries (Australia, Costa Rica, India, Indonesia, the Philippines), but *B. websteri* has so far only been described and reported from the USA.

Materials and methods

In 1983, on the Mountain Vas-hegy, close to the village Vaskeresztes, Vas County, Hungary, a handful of masticated cherry stones was found in an uninhabited hole of a fallen lime tree (*Tilia* sp.). The cherry stones were placed on blotting paper in Petri dishes, kept at room temperature and watered regularly. After some months a black layer of spiny perithecia appeared on the stones. Some of them were removed with a needle, placed on a microscope slide in a droplet of lactophenol, and examined under a light microscope (LM).

The material is deposited in the Mycological Herbarium of the Botanical Department of the Hungarian Natural History Museum (BP 100 344).

Results and discussion

Study of the perithecia, asci and ascospores resulted in the identification of the fungus as:

Boerlagiomyces websteri Shearer & J.L. Crane, *Mycologia* 87[1995]: 876, 1996.

Ascomata (Fig. 1) brown, pyriform, rostrate, membranous, setose, ca 300–400 × 200 µm. **Asci** few, two-spored, rounded at apex, tapering at base to a short stalk. **Ascospores** (Fig. 2) oblong, broadly rounded at ends, 75–105 × 35–42 µm, at first hyaline becoming dark brown and opaque, with nine transverse septa and one to three vertical septa within each transverse segment, with a thin gelatinous coat around the ascospores that more or less disappears at maturity.

The presence of *Boerlagiomyces websteri* outside the USA, i.e. in Hungary, shows that this fungus must be more widespread. It demonstrates also how imperfect the global mycobiota is known. Regarding its classification, *B. websteri* was recently shown to group with *Rhytisma acerinum* (*Rhytismatales*) in the *Pezizomycotina*, and it should possibly be excluded from the *Tubeufiaceae* (Kodsueb *et al.* 2006).

Fig. 1. An ascocarp (ascoma) of *Boerlagiomyces websteri*, isolated from old cherry stones. Bar = 100 μ m

Fig. 2. Ascospores of *Boerlagiomyces websteri* in LM. Note the nine transverse septa and one to three vertical septa within each transverse segment, visible in the immature, hyaline ascospores. Bar = 50 μ m

References

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